

Critical Thinking's Use in English Reading Instruction

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Abstract: After examining various definitions of critical thinking, most researchers agree on one point: critical thinking encompasses not only critical thinking dispositions such as clarity, accuracy, precision, consistency, sound evidence, good reasons, depth, breadth, and fairness, but also critical thinking skills, involving analysis, interpretation, inference, explanation, evaluation, and self-regulation. Thus, a novel approach to teaching English reading that emphasises helping pupils become critical thinkers need to be put forth. Critical readers who are able to "question, organise, interpret, synthesise, and digest what they read" should be taught to students.

Key words: critical thinking, English teaching, English reading.

THE IDEA OF CRITICAL THINKING AND ITS MANY DEFINITIONS

Since its inception about 2500 years ago, the idea of critical thinking has been expanded upon and improved. There are a number of definitions available in the literature that may be used to better comprehend the nature of critical thinking. The term "reflective thinking" (p.99-116) refers to the active, persistent, and careful consideration of a belief or supposed form of knowledge in light of the grounds which support it and the further conclusions to which it tends. John Dewey (1993) is the first to define critical thinking. He also proposed a five-phase model of critical thinking that included the following steps: (1) problem definition; (2) suggestions; (3) hypothesis generation; (4) reasoning; and (5) hypothesis testing.

According to Dewey, people must actively and consistently engage in their own thought processes by reflecting, providing justifications and interpretations for their findings, and assessing them. Reflective thinking processes lead to improved learning.

After examining various definitions of critical thinking, most researchers agree on one thing: critical thinking encompasses critical thinking dispositions such as clarity, accuracy, precision, consistency, relevance, sound evidence, good reasons, depth, breadth, and fairness, in addition to critical thinking skills (which include both a thinking process and thinking ability) involving analysis, interpretation, inference, explanation, evaluation, and self-regulation (Scriven & Paul, 1987).

BLOOM'S TAXONOMY ON CRITICAL THINKING PROCESS

In an effort to make the taxonomy more relevant for instructors and students in the twenty-first century, a new assembly was conducted by Lorin Anderson, a former Bloom student, during the 1990s. The word form of the previous taxonomy was changed from noun to verb in the new version. Understanding makes things memorable. The previous version's evaluation was replaced with evaluate, and it was positioned second from the bottom in the updated version. Understanding and creation need a shift in synthesis and comprehension. Each component has a thorough explanation in the table that follows. The vocabulary used to analyse the critical thinking abilities in literature has been clarified and updated in the new edition. The following provides an explanation of the new terminology. Examples will show how critical thinking functions in a piece of text. 1. Remembering: Retrieving, recognizing, and recalling relevant knowledge from long-term memory. 2. Understanding: Constructing meaning from oral, written, and graphic messages through interpreting, exemplifying, classifying, summarizing, inferring, comparing, and explaining. 3. Applying: Carrying out or using a procedure through executing, or implementing. 4. Analyzing: Breaking material into constituent parts, determining how the parts relate to one another and

to an overall structure or purpose through differentiating, organizing, and attributing. 5. Evaluating: Making judgments based on criteria and standards through checking and critiquing. 6. Creating: Putting elements together to form a coherent or functional whole; reorganizing elements into a new pattern or structure through generating, planning, or producing. (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001, p.67-68)

A MODEL FOR TEACHING ENGLISH READING & CONCLUSION

Students are primarily trained to develop their language abilities in a regular English reading class. This includes expanding their vocabulary first and then working on their reading comprehension skills. It is anticipated that they will learn something from the material and agree with the concepts or points of view that are discussed in the textbook. There are relatively few argumentative pieces with rigorous reasoning among the reading articles; the majority are literary works, amusing tales, and scientific papers (Wen et Liu, 2006). Multiple-choice questions are frequently used in reading assignments to assess pupils' comprehension. In order to encourage students' critical thinking, typical lectures and classroom activities are not particularly beneficial. Thus, a fresh approach to teaching English reading that emphasises helping students grow as critical thinkers has to be suggested. Critical readers who are able to "question, organise, interpret, synthesise, and digest what they read" should be taught to students (Paul, 1995, p. 491).

A defined five-step methodology has been developed based on research to encourage critical thinking in English reading classes. First action: Pre-reading: Giving pupils an overview of their history or culture. Understanding the text and outlining each paragraph's primary concept is the second stage. Step three is to examine the text's logical flow. Paul's Elements of Thought is a helpful resource at this level. Step four: Assessing the text's logical flow. Assessing the logic of the reading text aids in raising reading and thinking abilities to a higher degree as evaluation is one of the fundamental critical thinking skills. Writing is the fifth step. After understanding and analysing the material, students will be expected to write summaries, commentary, read journals, write their own comparable stories, or make arguments in a similar way. The higher level thinking abilities of synthesis and application are trained to the pupils in this stage. According to Brown's (2001) approach of language instruction, reading proficiency will be best fostered in conjunction with writing, speaking, and listening activities. The easiest way to accomplish your goals is to take advantage of the relationships between abilities, particularly the reading-writing connection, even in classes that are categorised as "reading." (page 283)

The first and second phases in this paradigm are focused on text interpretation, the third and fourth steps are on text assessment, and the fifth step is on the reader's response. It comes to the conclusion that this technique approaches teaching English reading in a highly novel and effective way. Of sure, the practice has to be improved. Therefore, recommendations from all professionals and academics are highly needed to ensure that the model operates flawlessly.

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